

THE ROLE OF ELECTRONIC MARKETING DIMENSIONS AND THEIR REFLECTION IN SALES VOLUME A FIELD STUDY APPLIED TO THE BAIWESHT COMPANY FOR MANUFACTURING LINA CHIPS IN SULAYMANIYAH GOVERNORATE

CHIYA MOHAMMED ALI ¹, ABBAS OMAR ABDALLA ² and
MOHAMMED SAEED QADIR ³

^{1,2,3} Sulaimani Polytechnic University / Chamchamal Technical Institute.

Email: ¹ chiya.ali@spu.edu.iq, ² abbas.omer@spu.edu.iq, ³ mohammed.saeed@spu.edu.iq

Abstract

The dimensions of electronic marketing are important to any company in general. The dimensions of electronic marketing were chosen in this research to identify their impact on maximizing the sales volume of business companies. The research problem included several fundamental questions revolving around all the dimensions of electronic marketing represented by electronic service, electronic promotion, and electronic distribution within E-marketing in maximizing the sales volume of a business company, and the research aimed to provide theoretical and field features for the researched company on the impact that e-marketing plays in enhancing sales and identifying the extent to which companies practice the dimensions of e-marketing from the point of view of e-marketing departments, and the importance of the research began on identifying the most dimensions of marketing. Electronic technology plays a role on the volume of sales by indicating the existence of a relationship or not and indicating the strength of the relationship if it exists. The data was collected using a questionnaire that was distributed to the research community represented by the Baiwesht Company for manufacturing Lina chips in Sulaymaniyah Governorate. The research sample was the employees of that company by 50 individuals. As for the methods The statistics used for the research included frequency and proportional distributions, arithmetic means, standard deviation, and correlation coefficient, using the computer program (SPSS). The research was based on a main hypothesis: Is there a statistically significant relationship between e-marketing and the company's sales volume? The most prominent results were the high level of awareness of the individuals under research. With the importance of each dimension of electronic marketing, it is clear that the researched company is greatly concerned with electronic service, electronic promotion, and electronic distribution of its products in the market and trying to maximize its sales. The researched company develops the services it provides to its customers in order to greatly maximize its sales, and the researched company's directions in the field of increasing its sales focus on The entry of new and fresh parts into the current market, and this means that the current market (customers) are more inclined to consume and demand its products. One of the research's recommendations is that the intensity of competition at the present time and the development of customers' needs and desires have made customers the point upon which the company relies in determining its needs, which requires the support of marketing elements. Electronically, with the aim of creating value for the customer, and working to use direct communication between the company and its customers.

Keywords: Electronic Marketing, Electronic Service, Electronic Promotion, Electronic Distribution, Sales Volume.

INTRODUCTION

E-marketing is one of the basic contemporary concepts that has been able, during the past few years of the current millennium, to leapfrog all marketing efforts and activities into contemporary trends in line with the current era and its variables, by using various tools, advanced methods, and modern technology in implementing marketing operations and activities in particular. With regard to marketing communications, information technology, product presentation, and completing marketing operations through multiple messages, the dimensions of electronic marketing play an important and effective role in maximizing sales volume. This importance has increased recently due to the tremendous technological developments in the field of selling products and their arrival to customers in a faster time than before Baiwesht Company for manufacturing Lina chips in Sulaymaniyah Governorate, in order to keep pace with developments and reach a high level of competition with major local and international companies in this field, and to achieve three important goals in the process of any commercial business producing chips, which are (higher quality, less time, and less effort).

The first axis of the research dealt with the research methodology, while the second axis focused on the theoretical framing of electronic marketing, its dimensions, and the theoretical starting points for sales volume. The third axis presented the field aspect of the research, while the research concluded with the fourth axis, which was devoted to the most important conclusions and proposals related to the research variables.

THE FIRST AXIS

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

First/research problem:

Production companies spend large sums of money in the field of electronic marketing, and for the purpose of knowing whether these expenditures achieve the desired results or not, researchers sought to study the role of these dimensions in the level of sales volume, and then the research problem arises through the role of these dimensions on sales volume, Which of these dimensions contributes to changing the volume of sales more than others, and based on this research problem, the research seeks to answer the following questions:

1. What is the reality and concept of electronic marketing and its impact on the volume of sales in production companies?
2. What are the dimensions of electronic marketing for customer service in the company under study?
3. What is the nature of the relationship between the dimensions of electronic marketing and sales volume?
4. What is the impact that electronic marketing has on changing the volume of sales?

Second: Research objectives:

The research aims to the following:

1. Identify the extent of awareness of customers of production companies in the Kurdistan Region:
 - The concept and importance of electronic marketing.
 - The role of electronic marketing in strengthening the relationship between companies and their customers.
 - The impact of electronic marketing on the quality of its products.
2. Evaluating the level of electronic marketing dimensions used by the researched companies.
3. Determine the role that the dimensions of electronic marketing play in the volume of sales.

Third: The importance of research:

The importance of the research lies in the following points:

1. Highlighting the nature of the relationship between the dimensions of electronic marketing and sales volume.
2. Determine the electronic marketing dimension that has the most impact on changing the volume of sales.
3. Knowing the electronic marketing dimension most used by the researched company.

Fourth: Hypothetical research plan:

The hypothetical plan for the research included the independent variable represented by the dimensions of electronic marketing (electronic service, electronic promotion, electronic distribution), while the dependent variable is sales, as shown in Figure (1)

Fifth: Research hypothesis:

There is a statistically significant relationship between electronic marketing and sales volume.

Sub-hypothesis:

1. There is a statistically significant relationship between electronic service and sales volume.
2. There is a statistically significant relationship between electronic promotion and sales volume.
3. There is a statistically significant relationship between electronic distribution and sales volume.

Sixth/ Limits of research:

1. Spatial boundaries: The spatial boundaries of the research were represented by the employees of the Baiwesht Company for manufacturing Lina chips, the research sample, whom the researchers were able to reach and distribute questionnaire forms to, and who are within the geographical boundaries of the city of Sulaymaniyah.
2. Time limits: The period limited to 6/1/2023 and 9/1/2023 can be counted, because it is the period during which this research was completed, starting with the initiation of the tasks of collecting data from the researched community and ending with the completion and printing of the research.

THE SECOND AXIS

E-marketing and its dimensions:

First: The concept of electronic marketing: The term electronic marketing appeared as one of the new and innovative concepts in the world, which led to the transformation of marketing in various regional and international service sectors in general, especially the electronic appearance sector, which turned the world into a small village that is not bound by the barriers of place or location. Time from traditional marketing to electronic marketing (Muhammad and Al-Ashqar, 2018, 255), and electronic marketing refers to all marketing activities that were carried out via the Internet, which is the management of interaction between the organization and the consumer in the space of the virtual environment in order to achieve common benefits and the virtual environment for electronic marketing. It relies primarily on Internet technology and the electronic marketing process does not focus on the process of selling products to the consumer only, but rather focuses on managing the relationships between the organization and the consumer on the one hand and between the elements of the internal environment and the external environment on the other hand (Secret of the Seal, 2012, 34). The Internet is the effective means used. In electronic marketing, in addition to telemarketing, telex, fax, interactive television, and e-mail are ways to send information about products, conduct market research, study competitor conditions, and correspond with customers. Therefore, it is a faster, simpler, and less expensive means than any other means of communication (Pakinson,

2002:99). E-marketing is “a type of buying and selling process between customers and producers using modern information and communications technology” (Booth, 2000:) E-marketing can be defined as “the use of electronic means in conducting reciprocal commercial transactions between the parties concerned instead of direct communication operations” or It is the process of buying and selling goods and services via the Internet (Sabra, 2010, 44), and electronic marketing is defined (Mahmoud, 2013, 3) as “the use of information and communications technologies in general and the Internet in particular to perform marketing activities in a way that ensures the benefit of the organization and the customer at the time Himself .

In light of these definitions, (Kenneth & Laudon, 2003, 108) believe that electronic marketing has two basic principles:

1. E-marketing is based on the automation of operating orders between the organization and beneficiaries using computers, mobile phones, or other communication technologies.
2. Electronic marketing is based on the principle of interactivity, where the term interactive marketing refers to the ability to address or send a message to an individual and receive that individual's answers. Thus, interactivity between the organization and the beneficiary leads to the concept of customer orientation by establishing direct relationships with him and identifying his real needs and satisfying them in the way that Check customer satisfaction.

Finally, and from the previous concepts, (Bashar, 2021) believes that the importance of electronic marketing did not come out of nowhere, but rather the strategic importance of electronic marketing increased after this activity opened new horizons in the world of marketing and provided organizations with great opportunities to increase targeted customers and large promotional capacity for two important reasons: Increasing the marketing uses of the Internet, as well as the important characteristics that electronic marketing has.

Second: Characteristics of electronic marketing: Electronic marketing is characterized by the characteristics of the Internet. These characteristics must be understood to make the marketing process successful, and they are as follows: (Mike, Zeitraum, Betreuer, 2006:30):

1. Extensive service: Electronic marketing is characterized by the fact that it provides a broad service, which enables customers dealing with the marketing site to access the site at any time, and without knowing the companies that own the site. (Al-Zoubi, 2015, 467).
2. Electronic marketing is characterized by the use of the element of excitement and attention used in electronic messages, as is the case in television advertisements, due to the multiplicity of companies that offer their electronic messages (Abdul Salam, and Ahmed, 20006: 131).
3. Due to the capabilities of the Internet to reach a large number of customers on an unprecedented scale, the importance of avoiding insincere marketing that does not carry real and appropriate content increases, because it is easy to spread this information about the company via the Internet from one of the customers who is exposed to a situation of

deception or failure. Honesty from a company (Abd Rabbo, 2011, 10).

4. Electronic communications through interactive electronic marketing. Because of this two-way communication, the possibilities of building strong relationships with customers around the world increase.
5. Directed sending ability: The Internet has enabled organizations to identify their customers, even before making a purchase, because digital technology makes it possible for website visitors to identify themselves and provide information about needs and desires before making a purchase.
6. Interactivity: This is the ability of customers to express needs and desires directly to the system in response to the marketing communications carried out by the organization (Pride & Ferrell, 2012, 60).

Third: Types of electronic marketing: Some experts in marketing (Kotler & Amstrong, 213, 77) believe that the marketing practiced by organizations can be classified into three main types:

1. External marketing: It is linked to traditional marketing functions such as designing and implementing the marketing mix (product, pricing, distribution, promotion).
2. Internal marketing: It is linked to employees within the organization, as the organization must follow effective policies to train employees, motivate them to have good communications with customers, and support employees to work as a team that seeks to satisfy the needs and desires of customers.
3. Interactive marketing: It is linked to the idea that the quality of services and goods provided to customers depends primarily and intensively on the quality and the relationship between the seller and the buyer.

Fourth: Dimensions of the effectiveness of electronic marketing in productivity companies:

E-marketing has contributed to establishing customer confidence and raising his level of satisfaction, and this leads to the excellence of productivity companies. In order for the e-marketing process to succeed and be a successful and effective process, it must have the following dimensions (Abu Fara, 2004, 142)

1. Electronic service to achieve benefit for the customer: The organization should seek to provide a sufficient and clear benefit by offering the product (good or service) via the Internet, as the level of this benefit results in the customer's decision to repeat or not repeat the purchase process.
2. Electronic promotion: The contents of the store and its various services should be displayed on the website in a way that suits the new nature of business (electronic business).

The display of the various contents of the online store should be different from the methods used in the field of traditional business, and the content of the electronic store's website should include aspects Basic marketing is: (Ghailani, 2015, 36)

- a) Providing the necessary and sufficient information about the products offered via the Internet.
 - b) Enabling the customer to communicate and interact with important elements in the marketing process.
 - c) Achieving the exchange process effectively, and this requires providing everything that meets needs and desires.
 - d) Simple and innovative construction of the online store website.
3. Electronic distribution: Distribution is the last dimension of electronic marketing and is defined by (Azzam, 2008, 297) as the process through which the good or service is made available in the place and in the appropriate quantity when the consumer desires it through electronic websites.

Fifth: The importance of electronic distribution: The electronic distribution function is considered one of the most important electronic marketing functions. This function provides the exchange processes that take place between both producers and consumers, and saves the effort and time of these consumers in obtaining the products they desire, in addition to adding values to the products as they It creates many benefits for it, possessory benefits by transferring its ownership (Ghoneim, 2009, 36).

The sales:

Sales are the products (goods and services) offered by producers and sellers to the buyer after the success of the sale process between the two parties, which represents the process of exchanging benefits between the seller and the buyer after paying the value of what is sold by the buyer to the seller with complete conviction between the two parties. Sales are analyzed by studying It provides details about the part represented by net sales in the company's profit and loss statement. It is the result of reviewing and auditing the company's records as contained in the business results and income statements, which show net sales and total profit, as it includes dividing the total sales data into categories.

It aims to find strengths and weaknesses. It not only helps in evaluating and controlling marketing efforts, but also helps in improving the formulation of goals and strategies and managing non-marketing activities such as production planning, inventory management, etc., as this analysis's mission is to trace sales revenue to its sources, whether through specific products, the sales area, and the analysis helps The business marketing manager determines the direction of future efforts regarding profitable products, changes in the sales area, decisions to abandon the production of certain products, or any other marketing efforts.

This analysis is done through several inputs that include the characteristics of the customer (including the reason for purchase, type of company, user versus intermediary). Product

characteristics (model, size, purchase of auxiliary equipment), geographical area (sales area, city, country, region) and demand size (large or small order rate, minimum requirement) (Nima, 2017, 28)

Strategic options to maximize sales volume:

According to (Jobber, 2004, 327), there are several strategic options to maximize sales volume, which are (market penetration, market expansion, product development, market development, and diversification, as shown in Figure 2). It will be explained as follows:-

1- Market penetration

It is the strategy for sales growth for current products in current markets that depends on winning the competitor's customers (this is done through the effective use of promotion, distribution, and reducing the price) and concluding a deal with the competitor (which leads to immediate increases in sales) and for the company to place barriers to prevent the entry of competitors (through reducing Labor costs, raw materials, and economies of scale. (Mullins & et al, 2008,442) adds that in order to penetrate the market significantly to obtain the total sales volume from the targeted customers, this is done by determining the number of current customers in the segment and then penetrating the product into this segment. After that, the frequency of customers purchasing the company's products is determined. (Peter & Donnelly, 2007, 12) stated that the market penetration strategy focuses mainly on reducing the price and offering advertisements that lead to several benefits as well, through filling and wrapping the product in different sizes or making the product available in stores. Many places and use modern methods to produce a more efficient product. (David, 2011, 141) adds that there are five indications of the possibility of using this strategy, which are (when the current markets are not saturated for a specific product, when the rate of use of current customers can increase significantly, when The market share of major competitors is declining when overall industry sales are increasing, when the correlation between dollar sales and marketing dollar agreement is previously high, and when savings or expansion in economies are key competitive advantages).

2- Expanding the market

The primary goal of this strategy is to expand the number of potential customers by targeting unserved markets, segments, or areas. This is done by converting customers who are not targeted for the company's products into customers who use it, or by increasing the rate of users of the company's products. Thus, sales growth is achieved by increasing the volume of The market (Jobber, 2004, 329).

3- Product development

It is one of the marketing opportunities that the company can use for new products or improve the current products of the product line and introduce them to current markets, that is, developing products for current markets. It is also a strategy that includes increasing sales through developing existing products or developing new products for current markets through improvement, style, and performance. The Authority aims to obtain an increase in sales to

current markets, and this is done through three different forms: expanding current product lines to give more choice to current customers, and changing the product through updating old products and innovation through fundamental development of different products (Nima, 2017, 29), and he adds (David, 2011, 143) There are five indications for using this strategy effectively, which are (when the company has successful products in the manufacturing stage of the product life cycle, and this idea is to attract customers to try the new product as an introduction to their positive experience of the company's current products, when the company competes in manufacturing... Certain characteristics of rapidly developing technology, when competitors' main efforts are to produce products of better quality compared to prices, when the company's competitors in the industry are high-growth, and when the company has strong research and development capabilities (especially)).

4- Market development

It is market development by identifying and developing sales for new market segments for existing products (Kotler & Armstrong, 2012, 45). To ensure growth in sales, the market is developed by finding new customers for existing products, as current products are marketed in new markets by promoting existing products that are of importance. In sales growth, David (2011, 142) adds six indicators for this strategy to be effective, which are (when there are new distribution channels available, reliable, inexpensive, and of high quality, when the company is very successful in what it offers, when there are new, available non-target markets, When the company has the required capital as well as human resources to perform expanded operations, when the company has surplus capacity to absorb production, and when the company's core industry develops a global perspective and speed).

5- Entering new markets (diversification)

The company seeks to offer new products to customers it has not served (Petr & Donnelly, 2007, 13), and (Jobber, 2004, 329) adds that it includes entering new markets for new products, which is one of the riskiest options, but it is necessary when the current products in the markets are growing little. He added (David, 2011, 143) Companies created difficulty in performing diverse business activities. The trend in the 1960s and 1970s was to diversify industrial businesses, as it is not possible to rely on a single industry, and the industry that relies on diversification must achieve sufficiently high returns and the investment must be stable.

THE THIRD AXIS

Describing the research variables, diagnosing them, and testing its hypotheses

First: Description of the personal characteristics of the respondents:

1- Gender: Table (1) shows that the largest percentage of respondents are females, as their percentage reached (62%), or (31) individuals, while the percentage of males reached (38%), i.e. (19) individuals. This indicates that the majority of employees In the researched organization they are from the female category.

Table (1): Distribution of respondents according to gender

S	Sex	Repetition	Percentage
1	Male	19	%38
2	Female	31	%62
Sum		50	100%

Source: Prepared by researchers based on questionnaire form data and SPSS results

2- Age: It is clear from the results of Table (2) that the majority of the respondents are less than 30 years old, which constituted (60%) of them, followed by the age group (30 - 39) years, and their percentage was (20%), then the age group Which is (40-49) with a percentage of (14%), while the age group came (over 49 years) and its percentage was (6%). These percentages confirm that the majority of employees in the organization under investigation are from age groups below (less than 30 years) in accordance with the nature of the work.

Table (2): Distribution of respondents according to age groups

S	age categories	Repetition	Percentage
1	Less than 30years old	30	%60
2	30 – 39	10	%20
3	40 – 49	7	%14
4	Over 49years old	3	%6
the total		50	100%

Source: Prepared by researchers based on questionnaire form data and SPSS results

3- Academic achievement: It is clear from Table (3) that individuals with a diploma degree came in first place with a percentage of (64%), then those with a bachelor’s degree, whose percentage reached (32%). This indicates that the majority of individuals responding are Of those who hold a diploma. This is due to the fact that the researched organization is a productive organization, so it is in greater need of those who hold a diploma.

Table (3): Distribution of respondents according to academic achievement

S	Academic achievement	Repetition	percentage
1	diploma	32	%64
2	Bachelor's	18	%36
the total		50	100%

Source: Prepared by researchers based on questionnaire form data and SPSS results

Second: Arithmetic means and standard deviations for the dimensions of organizational culture and the learning organization:

Table (4): Arithmetic means and standard deviations for the dimensions of electronic marketing

S	ferries	Arithmetic mean	standard deviation
first	Electronic service		
1	The company updates and renews its services on its websites 3.47	4.44	0.720
2	The company provides good information about its products through its websites 3.104 3.104	3.96	.856
3	The company is ready to answer customer questions in a short time 2.918	3.64	.722
4	The electronic services provided have an important impact on customer satisfaction 2.789	3.68	.891
5	The quality of electronic services has an impact on new customers 2.228	3.46	1.232
second	Electronic promotion		
6	Through social networking sites, it answers customer inquiries 3.533	4.44	.907
7	The company targets a wide range of existing customers 3.25	4.14	.881
8	Customer participation through their suggestions and recording comments and complaints via contacting the company's email 2.9	3.70	.789
9	The company uses social media to introduce its new products 3.3	4.16	.792
10	The company relies on advertising in the media as an effective tool for electronic promotion 2.7	3.96	1.177
third	Electronic distribution		
11	The company provides electronic distribution channels to distribute its products without relying on traditional distribution facilities 3.11	4.04	1.029
12	Electronic distribution channels facilitate contacting final consumers and trying to sell the product to them 3.168	3.92	.752
13	Through electronic distribution channels, the company enables consumers to place orders for its products 3.057	3.96	.903
14	The company is interested in modern electronic distribution methods to attract new customers and gain their loyalty 2.739	3.76	1.021
15	The company follows up on customer reactions and interests regarding electronic distribution channels 2.65	3.78	1.130
	Overall index		

Source: Prepared by researchers based on questionnaire form data and SPSS results

It is noted from Table (4), which shows the arithmetic means and standard deviations for the dimensions of electronic marketing, that paragraph (1) of the electronic service dimension (the company updates and renews its services on its websites), obtained a high arithmetic mean (4.44) according to the scale Likert quintile and less dispersion (0.720), which indicates that the surveyed organization is working to modernize and develop its electronic services with the aim of gaining new customers. As for paragraph (5), which states (the quality of electronic services has an impact on new customers), it received a low response rate (2.228). The dispersion was above average by (1.232), which reflects that the organization, despite its interest in developing its electronic services, did not achieve the desired rate of acquiring new customers.

Table (5): Arithmetic means and standard deviations for sales volume

S	Ferries	Arithmetic mean	standard deviation
1	The company achieves more sales when it penetrates the market by allowing the product to be available in several places 3.072	4.04	.968
2	The company achieves high sales through current product development 2.877	3.88	1.003
3	The company reduces or eliminates products offered that are in low demand 2.714	3.74	1.026
4	Increased sales by entering new markets 3.065	3.98	.915
5	The company increases its sales according to the indicators obtained in the current market by 2.94	4.08	1.140
Overall index			

Source: Prepared by researchers based on questionnaire form data and SPSS results

It is noted from Table (5), which shows the arithmetic means and standard deviations for the dependent variable (sales volume), that we find that Paragraph (1), which is that (the company achieves more sales when it penetrates the market by allowing the product to be present in several places), has occurred. It received a high response rate (4.04) and little dispersion (0.968), which indicates that providing the product in different places enables the company to achieve more sales. As for paragraph (3) (The company reduces or eliminates the products provided that are in low demand.) it received a high response rate (4.04). The answers are low (3.74) and the dispersion is above the average by (1.028), which indicates that the organization will not exclude products provided with low demand.

Third: Determine the level of relative importance of electronic marketing and sales volume

The results of the response of members of the research sample regarding the dimensions of electronic marketing and sales volume shown in Table (6) regarding the values of the arithmetic means and standard deviations resulted in the following:

Table (6): Arithmetic means and standard deviation for electronic marketing and sales volume

Variables	E-Marketing				Sales volume
	Electronic service	Electronic promotion	Electronic distribution	Overall index	Overall index
Arithmetic mean	3.836	4.08	3.892	3.936	3.944
standard deviation	0.942	0.902	0.967	0.937	1.010
	2.892	3.178	2.925	2.999	2.934

From the above-mentioned table, the researchers summarize the results:

1. The arithmetic means and standard deviations for the dimensions of the explanatory variable (e-marketing) were as shown in Table (6), where the arithmetic mean for the e-service dimension was (3.836) with a dispersion of (0.942), which shows that the level of the index of this dimension was moderate among the sample members, while We note that the electronic promotion dimension obtained an arithmetic mean of (4.08) and a standard deviation of (0.902), which is a level above the average, which indicates the appropriate objective dealing of the sample members with the dimensions of electronic marketing. As

for the arithmetic mean of the electronic distribution dimension, it reached (3.892) and a deviation A standard value of (0.967), and thus the general mean of the electronic marketing variable among the sample members is at an average level of (3.936) and a dispersion of (0.937). This result indicates the extent of the researched organization's interest in electronic marketing in its various dimensions.

2. The arithmetic mean of the sales volume variable among sample members showed an average level of (3.944) and a dispersion of (1.010). This result indicates that the dimensions of electronic marketing had a positive impact on increasing sales volume.

Fourth: Testing the study plan and hypotheses

1- Analyzing the correlations between the study variables

This paragraph includes testing the validity of the first main hypothesis, which indicates (the existence of a significant correlation between the dimensions of electronic marketing and the volume of sales at the level of the overall index and at the level of the sub-dimensions. This hypothesis was tested using the Pearson correlation coefficient, and the results were as follows:

The main hypothesis: A correlation between the dimensions of e-marketing and the volume of sales at the aggregate level: This hypothesis states (there is a statistically significant effect between the dimensions of e-marketing and the volume of sales) at a level of statistical significance (0.05), in order to identify the nature of the positive correlation between the dimensions of e-marketing. And the volume of sales in the organization, the research sample, at the overall level. The data in table (7) indicates the presence of a significant correlation, as the value of the total correlation coefficient reached (0.560) at a significant level (0.05), and this indicates the strength of the relationship between the two main variables.

Table (7): Correlation coefficient between electronic marketing and sales volume

Independent dimension	E-Marketing
Approved dimension	
Sales volume	0.560**

At a significance level of 0.05 N=50

Source: Results of the electronic calculator (SPSS)

The study plan and hypotheses require determining the correlation between the dimensions of e-marketing and sales volume at the level of sub-dimensions through Table (7), and from following the correlation coefficients between the dimensions of e-marketing and sales volume, the following becomes clear:

The first sub-hypothesis: There is a positive significant correlation between the electronic service and sales volume, as the correlation value reached (0.560) at a significant level (0.05).

The second sub-hypothesis: There is a positive significant correlation between electronic promotion and sales volume, as the correlation value reached (0.670) at a significant level (0.05).

The third sub-hypothesis: There is a positive significant correlation between electronic distribution and sales volume, as the correlation value reached (0.457) at a significant level (0.05).

These relationships indicate that the more dimensions of electronic marketing are available in the organization under study, the more sales volume will be activated to a good degree, and through (electronic service, electronic promotion, and electronic distribution), because these dimensions have a prominent role in stimulating the increase in sales volume, and based on the above results. Correlation relationships at the macro and micro levels, we achieve proof of the validity of the first main hypothesis.

Table (8): results of the partial correlation between the dimensions of electronic marketing and sales volume at the overall level of the sample

Explanatory variable / Responsive variable	Dimensions of electronic marketing		
	Electronic service	Electronic promotion	Electronic distribution
Sales volume	0.560**	0.670**	0.457**

At a significance level of 0.05 N=50

Source: results of the electronic calculator (spss).

2- Analyzing the influence relationships between the study variables:

Based on the content of the main hypothesis, which indicates that there is a significant effect of the dimensions of electronic marketing in maximizing the volume of sales at the aggregate level and at the dimensional level, Table (9) shows indicators and results of the influence relationships of the dimensions of electronic marketing in increasing the volume of sales at the aggregate level and at the dimensional level, and they were Test results are as follows:

-Testing influence relationships at the macro level:

Table (9) shows that the dimensions of electronic marketing have a significant effect on increasing the volume of sales. This effect is supported by the value (F) of (24.855) at two degrees of freedom (1.60) and a level of significance (0.05), and it is inferred from the coefficient of determination (R) coupon of (0.56). %) This indicates that the dimensions of electronic marketing explain the value of (56%) of the respondent variable, which is represented by sales volume. This is supported by the value of the regression coefficient (0.540), and this was reinforced by the value of (T), which amounts to (7.634) at two degrees of freedom (1.60) and a level of significance (0.05).), and these results demonstrate the importance of the dimensions of electronic marketing in increasing the volume of sales in the organization under investigation, and this confirms the acceptance of the main hypothesis which states that there is a relationship of influence of the dimensions of electronic marketing on the volume of sales in the field under study.

Table (9): results of the impact relationship of the dimensions of electronic marketing on sales volume at the aggregate level

Responsive variable explanatory variable	Sales volume				
	B ₀	B ₁	R ²	F calculated	T calculated
E-Marketing					
Dimensions combined	0.255	0.540	0.560	24.855**	7.634**

Source: Results of the electronic calculator (SPSS) N=50 df(1.60) p=0.05

-Testing influence relationships at the micro level:

A- The effect of the electronic service on the volume of sales: The results of table (10) indicate that there is a significant effect of the electronic service on the volume of sales. This is supported by the value of (f) amounting to (0.773) at two degrees of freedom (1.60) and a level of significance (0.05), and it is inferred from the value of the coefficient Determination (R), which is (0.132%).

This indicates that the electronic service explains its value (13%) of the responding variable, which is the increase in sales volume. This is supported by the value of the regression coefficient (0.360), and this was reinforced by the value of (T), which is (10.570) at two degrees. Freedom (1.60) and significance level (0.05), which means that the main hypothesis has been achieved at the level of the first dimension.

B- The effect of electronic promotion on sales volume: The results of Table (10) indicate that there is a significant effect of electronic promotion on sales volume, and this is supported by the value of (f) amounting to (16.602) at two degrees of freedom (1.60) and a level of significance (0.05), and it is inferred from the value of the coefficient Determination (R), which is (0.22%).

This indicates that electronic promotion explains (22%) of the responding variable, which is the increase in sales volume. This is supported by the value of the regression coefficient (0.470), and this was reinforced by the value of (T), which is (7.470) at two degrees. Freedom (1.60) and significance level (0.05), which means that the main hypothesis has been achieved at the level of the second dimension.

C- The effect of electronic distribution on sales volume: The results of table (10) indicate that there is a significant effect of electronic distribution on sales volume. This is supported by the value of (f), which is (0.800) at two degrees of freedom (1.60) and a level of significance (0.05), and is inferred from the value of the coefficient Determination (R), which is (0.06%).

This indicates that electronic distribution explains its value (6%) of the responding variable, which is the increase in sales volume. This is supported by the value of the regression coefficient (0.260), and this was reinforced by the value of (T), which is (10.980) at two degrees. Freedom (1.60) and significance level (0.05), which means that the main hypothesis has been achieved at the level of the third dimension.

Table (10): Results of the influence relationship at the micro level

Responsive variable explanatory variable	Sales volume				
	B ₀	B ₁	R ²	F calculated	T calculated
Dimensions of electronic marketing	0.112	0.360	0.13	0.773**	10.570**
Electronic service	0.382	0.470	0.22	16.602**	7.470**
Electronic promotion	0.090	0.260	0.06	0.800**	10.980**

CONCLUSIONS

This was conducted to determine the relationship between the impact of electronic marketing on the volume of sales in the chips industries. The results of the study indicate the following:

1. The results of the research showed that there is a strong, direct correlation between electronic marketing in its dimensions and the volume of sales, that is, the more electronic marketing is used and it is used appropriately, this leads to the volume of sales and makes it more developed and advanced. It also showed that electronic marketing makes the consumer able to prepare a budget that suits his purchasing power. Electronic marketing also helps the consumer to prepare his budget, especially for purchasing, so the consumer chooses the product that suits his capabilities. Electronic marketing also contributes to shortening time and effort compared to traditional marketing, which makes it the best choice for customers. The current study differed with the study (Anser et al., 2020), which It stated that there is a relationship between information and communications technology, e-marketing, organizational readiness, and sales volume. The study also proved the existence of a correlation between the electronic service dimension and sales volume, as the correlation coefficient reached (0.560**) at a significant level (0.05). The study also proved the existence of a correlation between After electronic promotion and sales volume, the correlation coefficient reached (0.670**) at a significance level (0.05). The study also proved the existence of a correlation between the electronic distribution dimension and sales volume, where the correlation coefficient reached (0.457**) at a significance level (0.05).
2. The results of the study showed that there is an impact of electronic marketing, in its dimensions (electronic promotion, electronic service, electronic distribution), on the volume of sales at Chips Company. This indicates that the greater the use of electronic marketing in the company's transactions, this leads to an increase in the volume of sales, and the researcher attributes this result to To the point that the world is now heading to using the Internet in its various transactions in order to facilitate the selection process for consumers and save them time and effort in the age of speed, and this result differed with the result of a study (Tarek Mohamed, 2019) that there is an impact of electronic marketing on the size of products.
3. E-marketing helps increase sales in the organization because the costs are lower than traditional marketing.
4. E-marketing contributes to building a strong relationship between companies and their

customers through effective interaction through companies' platforms with their consumers.

5. Companies that use electronic marketing benefit from the ability to influence consumers' purchasing decisions.
6. Electronic marketing maintains the organization's customers and ensures their loyalty to it through the offers it provides;
7. The promotional mix affects sales activation and the purchasing behavior of consumers, as the sales stimulation method is more effective in companies that adopt electronic marketing.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. In the race for electronic transformation, the company needs, first and foremost, to identify its new electronic products, new forms of marketing, and explore new sales channels in order to interact with customers, in order to propose an integrated experience in all channels of interaction or purchase.
2. To achieve electronic transformation mechanically, the company must maintain direct contact with customers in the business sector, such as marketing and sales, production operations and human resources, via communications and information technology.
3. The necessity of educating workers about the importance of e-marketing and the information it provides in our current era in terms of global openness to markets. Therefore, greater attention must be paid to it. E-marketing also contributes to influencing consumer behavior and changing his opinions and decisions, so work must be done to expand its scope in offering services. ,
4. The necessity of having electronic guidance programs that explain how to search the electronic market for the consumer, and open the doors to strategic marketing alliances and partnerships between the company on the one hand, and other companies in Iraq and abroad on the other hand, to benefit from its reputation and long experience in this field,
5. Encouraging scientific research in the field of company work in general and electronic marketing in particular, and always being aware of the experiences of leading companies in the field of providing, marketing and promoting products, and working to apply these international experiences in the Iraqi production sector in the correct and appropriate manner for the region, and studying the role of electronic marketing with other variables. And different environments.

Sources

- 1) Abd Rabbo, Raed Muhammad, 2011, Electronic Marketing, Al-Janadriyah Publishing and Distribution, Amman, Jordan.
- 2) Abdul Salam Abu Qahf and Tariq Taha Ahmed, 2006, Advertising Engineering and Electronic Advertising, 1st edition.
- 3) Al-Qutji, Bashar Zakir Saleh, 2021, Employing electronic marketing in providing social services, Journal of Management and Economics, Volume 10, Issue 38, University of Mosul, Iraq.

- 4) Al-Zoubi, Ali Falah, 2015, Commercial Promotion and Advertising Department, Contemporary Introduction, Al-Masirah Publishing and Distribution, Amman, Jordan
- 5) Booth , R, 2000, E .Performance management.eventually, management accounting.
- 6) Ghilani, Shabila, 2015, electronic service marketing, a case study of the Algeria Telecommunications Organization Touggourt, a memorandum submitted to complete the requirements for an academic master's degree in media and communication sciences, Department of Media and Communication Sciences, Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences, University of Kasdi Merbah Ouargla, Algeria.
- 7) Ghoneim, Ahmed Mohamed, 2009, Marketing and E-Commerce, Modern Library for Publishing and Distribution, Egypt.
- 8) Kenneth C. Laudon & Janeplaudon.2003, Essential of management information manage systems. New Jersey : Prentice hall Inc .
- 9) Kotler.p. and Amstrong .2013 .Consumer Marketing and introduction. New York
- 10) Mahmoud, Suha Hassan, 2013, Evaluating the opportunities for applying electronic marketing and its impact on improving the quality of banking services, a field study on commercial banks in the city of Damascus, Master's thesis in Business Administration, Tishreen University, Damascus, Syria.
- 11) Mike, Zeitraum, Betreuer,2006,The Structure Of The E Marketing Mix “ University Of ST Gallen , February .
- 12) Muhammad Anhar Khairuddin, and Al-Ashqar, Saif, 2018, The role of electronic marketing in enhancing competitive advantage, a proposed electronic model for a virtual aviation organization, Cihan University Journal, Erbil Scientific, Special Issue, Issue 2, Volume B, Erbil, Iraq
- 13) Nima, Shaliba Al-Kaabi, 2018, The role of promotional mix tools in maximizing sales volume, Journal of Economic and Administrative Sciences, No. 102, Volume 24, College of Administration and Economics, University of Baghdad, Iraq.
- 14) Parkinson S ,2001 , Computers in Marketing .3rd.ed , oxford Butter Worth, Heinemann.u.k .
- 15) Prid William & Ferrell, oc, 2012 , Marketing Concepts And Strategies, Studented, Houghton Mifflin Co, U.S.A.
- 16) Samar Tawfiq Sabra, 2010, Electronic Marketing, first edition, Dar Al-Asaar, Al-Alami for Publishing and Distribution, Amman, Jordan.
- 17) Secret of the Seal, Muhammad, 2012, The impact of electronic marketing on the marketing mix of banking services, unpublished doctoral dissertation, Omdurman Islamic University, Sudan.
- 18) Youssef Ahmed Abu Fara, 2004, Electronic Marketing, Wael Publishing House, Amman, Jordan.